

SYSTEMATIC AND STRUCTURAL FEATURES OF TERMS IN ENGLISH ON THE TOPIC "AUTOMOBILIZATION"

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Annotation:

The purpose of the study is to analyze the structural and word-formation properties of English terminological units that form the subject area "Automobile". Based on the methods of component and definitional analysis, as well as methods of derivational and functional analysis of automotive terms, the most productive derivational models of automotive terms are identified; morphological and syntactic models of English automotive terms are described. The theoretical value of the study lies in the study of the professional and terminological vocabulary of the automotive sector in terms of establishing its meaning and role in the representation of the national language world.

Keywords: Term, subject area, automotive vocabulary, word formation, syntactic models.

INTRODUCTION

The relevance of the study of automotive terminology for the theory of language is due to extra linguistic and linguistic factors, as well as the tendency for general professional and highly specialized automotive terms to go beyond the boundaries of this subject area¹. The choice of American English for the study of the Automotive subject area is due to the significant influence of American automotive culture on the world community.

BACKGROUND KNOWLEDGE

¹ Хачмафова З.Р., Ефремов А.А. Актуализируемые признаки метафорического терминообразования (на материале терминологии американской нефтегазовой отрасли) // Вестник Адыгейского государственного университета. Сер. Филология и искусствоведение. Майкоп: Изд-во АГУ, 2013. Вып. 3 (126). С. 106-112.

An automotive term is a word or phrase that is the exact designation of the concept of the subject area "Automobile". The terminology of this subject area is understood as a set of terms of activity and knowledge related to the field of automobile and transport. Thus, we can say that the term is understood as a special word or phrase that functions in a certain professional area and in special conditions. The term is a verbal graphic designation of a concept that is included in the system of concepts of a particular subject area. It should be noted that the term, being a special sign of scientific discourse, "acts as a specific mental representation; the totality of all conceptually terminal representations forms a conceptual model of the scientific picture of the world"².

The formation of the subject area as a linguistic phenomenon is carried out on the basis of a number of typologically close processes, the most important of which is the complex process of reflecting and fixing in various facts of the language the realities of the extralinguistic reality of the world around us. Significant for our study is the opinion that "subject areas, or conceptual structures, are a specific reconstruction of human experience transformed into knowledge. The internal structuring of categories includes prototypes and is organized, among other things, through hierarchical and taxonomic relationships, as well as other types of relationships"³.

METHODOLOGY

In the course of this study, a significant number of terms in the subject area "Automobile", formed with the help of prefixation and suffixation, were identified and analyzed by analyzing and categorizing methods.

² Буянова Л.Ю. Термин как единица логоса: монография. 2-е изд., стер. Москва: Наука: Флинта, 2013. 224 с.

³ Тлехатук С.Р. Категориальное структурирование предметной области «Экономика» // Вестник Адыгейского государственного университета. Сер.: Филология и искусствоведение. Майкоп, 2017. Вып. 3 (202). С. 80-85.

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

It should be noted that the suffixes and prefixes of the English language, with the help of which automotive terms are formed, belong to the traditional word-forming means of the English language. In prefix formation, prefixes borrowed from Latin and Greek are quite productive: *anti-*, *auto-*, *dis-*, *de-*, *mono-*, *rever-*, *trans*, *uni-*, *multi-*, *re-*, as well as prefixes *over-*, *up-*, *under-*, which refer to morphemes characteristic of words of Germanic origin. For example: *anti-roll bar* "roll bar", *automatic choke* "automatic cold start", *de-fogger* "defrost, heated glass", *dis-placement* "displacement", *ex-haust system* "exhaust system", *in-let manifold*, *inter-cooler*, *outer*, *mono-block*, *multi van*, *overheating*, *rever-sing lights*, *reversing lights*, *pre-heating timer* "glow plug preheat timer", *sus-pention arm* "suspension arm", *trans-fer case* "transfer case", *under-steering* "understeer", *uni-versal joint* "gimbal joint", *up-holstery* "upholstery interior, seats", *im-purity* "pollution".

Among the presented suffixes in English, the most productive are suffixes borrowed from Latin, Greek and French: *-ment*, *-ture*, *-oid*, *-ance*, *-ible*, *-iv*, *-ic*, *-ission*, *-or*, *-er*, which corresponds to the general language situation in word-formation processes in English: *glove compart-ment* "box, glove compartment", *mix-ture* control "mixture composition control", *hyp-oid* gear "hypoid gear", *ground clearance* "ground clearance", *fus-ible link* "safety line", *evaporat-ive* "fumes suction system (from gas tank)", *electr-ic* "electric", *transm-ission* "transmission", *accelerat-or* "gas pedal", *air cleaner* "air filter".

Thus, the following most common combinations of **prefixes and suffixes** in the formation of the terminological vocabulary of the subject area "Automobile" in English have been identified: prefixes *de-*, *dis-*, *re-*, *in-*, with suffixes *-ment*, *-er*, *-ing*. For example, *displacement*, *disassambling*, *defogger*, *injector*, *regulator*, *replacement*, etc. In English, the phenomenon of conversion is one of the

productive ways of word formation and, accordingly, it seems important for studying the features of the formation of terminological vocabulary in various industry terminologies.

Conversion is “a kind of transposition, in which the transition of a word from one part of speech to another occurs in such a way that the nominative form of the word of one part of speech is used without any material changes as a representative of another part of speech”⁴.

In terms of their frequency and usage, the selected models correspond to the current trend in the field of word formation in the English language. Every language strives for economy in expression, and in term formation this tendency is especially manifested in abbreviation - **reduction** of words and phrases.

Abbreviation is a method of term formation that combines all types of complex abbreviated and abbreviated formations. In addition to words, abbreviations and phrases, therefore, this method of word formation should already be attributed to the morphological and syntactic composition of the terminological units of the subject area "Automobile" in English:

The component composition of the terminological units of the subject area "Car" in English:

1) two-part terms:

noun + noun, e.g. *air duct, air filter, arm rest, brake disk, charge indicator, check connector, seat belt*;

participle (adjective) + noun, e.g. *connecting rod, cooling system, filling station, reversing lights*;

2) three-part terms: noun + noun, e.g. *automatic performance control, automatic transmission fluid, central fuel injection, double overhead camshaft, diagnostic*

⁴ Kubryakova E. S., Gireev V. A. Conversion in modern English // Bulletin of VSU. Ser.: Linguistics and intercultural communication. 2002. No. 2. pp. 33–38.

test mode, electronic control unit, single overhead camshaft, progressive power steering, rear window defogger;

adjective + noun + noun, e.g. *automatic performance control, automatic transmission fluid, central fuel injection, double overhead camshaft, diagnostic test mode, electronic control unit, single overhead camshaft, progressive power steering, rear window defogger;*

noun + noun + noun, e.g. *air flow control, brake master cylinder, temperature heat water, vehicle identification number;*

prefix + adjective + noun, e.g. *anti-blocking system, multi-point fuel injection;*

3) four-part terms: adjective + noun + noun, e.g. *electronic brake control module, full size spare tire.*

An analysis of the structural composition of the terms of the subject area "Automobile" showed that in the studied subject area the following ratio of one-word and super-word units is revealed: - one-word terms: *boot, brake, cab, clutch, horn, jack, oil, pedal, pump, spring, van, wheel, lock, latch, hinge, lights, etc.*

- **derivatives:** *absorber, bumper, accelerator, cylinder, radiator, screwdriver, spanner, suspension, trailer, transmission, etc.*

- **complex:** *windscreen, windshield, speedometer, seatbelt, screwdriver, rearview, hubcap, highway, headrest, headlights, hatchback, dashboard, crankshaft, armrest, etc.*

- **terminology.**

For the English language, the formation of term combinations according to the **N + N** or **A + N** model is characteristic. The most productive models of term combinations: - *binary:*

a) **N+N models:** *brake fluid, brake light, car alarm, electrical system, driver's license, fan belt, fog lights, front door, fuel gauge, license plate, number plate, oil pump, rearview mirror, service station, spark plug, tail-light, temperature gauge, temperature gauge, windscreen wiper, traffic jam;*

b) based on the A+N model: *parking light, spare parts, steering wheel, spare tire*
multi-component: *gear-change shift lever, bumper-to-bumper, etc.*

The presented component analysis allows us to conclude that one of the elements of the term combination is a reference pointing to a generic feature of term. The attributive element of the term combination reveals the distinctive specific feature of the term. As a result of the study of the terms of the subject area "Automobile", we have identified the following types of abbreviations:

a) **letter abbreviations** (**A|W** - alloy wheels; **AFC** - Air Flow Control; **CPS** - Crank Position Sensor, etc.);

b) **syllabic abbreviations or partial abbreviations** consisting of a letter or syllable (**BAT** battery; **N** - neutral; **ALT** altitude; **LS** (left side), etc.);

c) **digital abbreviations** consisting of letters or syllables and numbers (**2 WAY O / D** - "automatic overdrive shutdown"; **4A / T** - "four-speed automatic transmission", etc.);

d) **truncated words** (**HAZ** (hazard) - "alarm"; **BARO** (barometric pressure) - "atmospheric pressure"; **CAT** - "catalyst"; **M / MAN** manu - "manual"; **URBO** - "turbocharging", etc.) .

During the analysis of abbreviations of terms, special methods of abbreviations were also identified, in which several abbreviations are used at once, for example:

AM 1 - power supply of the first group of contacts of the ignition lock; **AM 2** - power supply of the second group of contacts of the ignition switch; **HEAD LN** - left headlight; **HEAD RH** - right headlight, etc.

Of interest are metaphorized abbreviations such as **How-guide** (step-by-step) - detailed instructions (step by step) and **U-turn** - a 180-degree turn.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

One cannot but agree that "the appearance of a new word in a language is the result of a complex interaction between the mechanisms of categorization of the surrounding world and linguistic forms, non-linguistic and linguistic

knowledge”⁵.

Phrasal verbs of modern English are of interest in the process of term formation in the light of the theory of conceptual integration. The different degree of solidarity and the different nature of the influence of neighboring elements on the meaning of a phrasal verb make them an interesting object for analysis from the point of view of integration processes during their formation. Almost all phrasal verbs are formed by **metaphorization**. Consider the most common phrasal verbs that have become part of the automotive vocabulary. The phrasal verb *head to* means “to go, move”, for example: I’m heading to the university. The nuclear seme is *head*. The phrasal verb *back up* means that the cars are in a line, “*back to back*”, waiting opportunity to continue moving. The nuclear theme is *back*. Other phrasal verbs highlighted in the course of the analysis show a close connection with the nuclear theme, served as the basis for word formation. For example: *cut off* “cut someone.” Did you see how that guy just cut me off?!? Did you see this guy cut me?! The nuclear theme is *cut*. Also: *cone off* (narrowing of the road). The road cones off at the end of the street. The road narrows at the end of the street. The nuclear theme is *cone* “cut”. Thus, it is obvious that the process of merging scientific and naive worldviews has a significant impact on such a specific way of word formation inherent in the English language as phrasal verbs, the metaphorical nature of which allows them to become an integral part of the terminological system. In conclusion, we note that the study of the structural characteristics of terms, derivational models of branch terminological system is important for establishing ways to nominate the phenomena of the surrounding reality.

The structural analysis of English automotive terms showed that the main

⁵ Jespersen O. A modern English grammar on historical principles. Part II. London; Copenhagen: G. Allen & Unwin, 1954. 512 p.

methods of derivation of the subject area "Automobile" include affixation, syntactic method, word formation and abbreviation, as well as metaphorization.

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